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First record of the genus *Schizophragma* OGLOBLIN, 1949 (Hymenoptera: Mymaridae) in Europe

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Abstract: The genus *Schizophragma* OGLOBLIN (Hymenoptera: Mymaridae) is recorded for the first time from Europe. One male of an unidentified species, as illustrated, was collected in Niepołomice Forest, Lesser Poland Voivodeship, Poland. With this addition, the number of European Mymaridae genera has increased to 25.

Key words: Chalcidoidea, fairyfly, Poland, faunistics, West Palaearctic.

INTRODUCTION

Schizophragma OGLOBLIN, 1949 belongs to the *Anagrus* HALIDAY group of genera of Mymaridae (LIN *et al.* 2007). HUBER (1987) gave a diagnosis and provided a key to its seven known species: *S. basalis* OGLOBLIN, 1949, *S. bicolor* (DOZIER, 1932), *S. latipennis* (CRAWFORD, 1913), *S. parvula* OGLOBLIN, 1949, *S. peruana* OGLOBLIN, 1949, *S. saltensis* OGLOBLIN, 1949, and *S. squamosa* OGLOBLIN, 1949. Later, TRIAPITSYN (2018) transferred *S. saltensis*, which has an entire clava of the female antenna, to *Anagrus* and placed it in the stethynioides species group. A few years later, TRIAPITSYN (2021) described *S. mitai* TRIAPITSYN, 2021 from Japan and presented a key to the Old World species, along with new *Schizophragma* records. The new species was also later recorded from India (RAMESHKUMAR *et al.* 2023). Recently, HUBER *et al.* (2024) synonymized the fossil genus *Palaeopatasson* WITSACK, 1986 under *Schizophragma*, and its type species *P. grollei* WITSACK transferred to *Schizophragma*. The genus currently includes nine nominal species. It reaches its greatest diversity in the Neotropical region, but it is also known from the Nearctic, Oriental, Palearctic, Australasian, and Afrotropical regions (HUBER, 1987, LIN *et al.* 2007, REHMAT & ANIS 2014, KOPONEN & TRIAPITSYN, 2016). Various Membracidae (Hemiptera) serve as hosts for some species of *Schizophragma* (HUBER 1987).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The examined male was collected by T. Grzegorzczuk in IBL-2 screen trap in the Niepołomice Forest, Poland and later donated to the author. The specimen was chemically dried by immersion in absolute ethanol for several hours, then in isopropanol for several hours and then for one day in hexamethyldisilazane (HMDS). After HMDS evaporated, the specimen was mounted on a triangular cardboard point. A pair of wings and one antenna were

mounted on a microslide in Canada balsam. A Bresser Science TFM-301 Trino microscope paired with a Canon EOS 250D camera was used to photograph the specimens on slides. For imaging the dried specimen, a Laowa 25 mm f/2,8 2,5-5X Ultra Macro was used. The individual photos were stacked in Helicon Focus 8.0.0 (Helicon Soft Ltd.). All measurements are given in micrometers (μm).

RESULTS

Schizophragma OGLOBLIN, 1949

Schizophragma sp. (Figs 1–7)

Material examined. Poland: Lesser Poland Voivodeship, Niepołomice Forest, 11.VI.–20.VII.2017, coll. T. Grzegorzczuk, IBL-2 screen trap [1 ♂ in author's collection].

Diagnosis. Male. Body length 730. Head and body brown, antenna pale brown except pedicel, flagellomer 1 and flagellomer 2 slightly lighter, and legs pale brown.

Mesosoma (Fig. 2). Frenum with a pair of setae and divided longitudinally; mesophragma projected into gaster, and shallowly notched posteriorly.

Antenna (Figs 4–5). Antenna with 11 flagellomers; scape with distinct cross-ridges; all flagellomers with multiporous plate sensilla, longer than wide, and longer than pedicel, each flagellomere almost as long as scape.

Wings (Figs 6–7). Fore wing $3.4\times$ as long as wide; length/width ratio 780:230; longest marginal cilia $0.65\times$ maximum wing width; length 150. Hind wing $16\times$ as long as wide, length/width ratio 720:45; longest marginal cilia $2.4\times$ maximum wing width; length 110.

Distribution. Poland.

Host. Unknown.

Fig. 1. *Schizophragma* sp., male, habitus in ethanol (photo F. Pawluk).

Comments. It is probably a new, undescribed species endemic to Europe. However, the occurrence of *S. mitai* in Europe is also possible. The fore wing of the specimen presented here is very similar to that of *S. indica* REHMAT & ANIS, 2014, as illustrated by REHMAT & ANIS (2014). However, until the females are collected, it is not possible to identify or describe a potentially new species based on a single male.

Figs. 2–5. *Schizophragma* sp., male. 2. Mesosoma in ethanol. 3. Habitus, dry-mounted. 4. Scape and pedicel. 5. Antenna (photo F. Pawluk).

Figs. 6–7. *Schizophragma* sp., male. 6. Fore wing. 7. Hind wing (photo F. Pawluk).

DISCUSSION

This is the first record of *Schizophragma* in Europe and the third known locality from the Palearctic region. *Schizophragma bicolor* (DOZIER, 1932) was recorded from the Canary Islands (KOPONEN & TRIAPITSYN 2016), but it is distributed in the Neotropical and Nearctic region. This record is unlikely to be attributable to an endemic European species and rather reflects a recent expansion. More southern species may extend their ranges to northern Europe, like recently recorded in Finland *Anagrus optabilis* (PERKINS, 1905), for instance (TRIAPITSYN *et al.* 2020). The current European entomofauna of Mymaridae comprises 23 genera (SAMKOVÁ *et al.* 2020), after *Caraphractus* WALKER, 1846 was synonymised under *Eustochus* HALIDAY, 1933 by TRIAPITSYN *et al.* (2020). Currently, together with the recently recorded *Dicopomorpha* OGLOBLIN, 1955, by PAWLUK (unpublished data), the number of mymarid genera in Europe has increased to 25.

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